

THE STATUS OF A PEDAGOGUE IN NEW UZBEKISTAN: SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL CLASSIFICATION AND SPECIFIC FEATURES

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Abstract: In the article, the socio-philosophical aspects of securing the status of a pedagogue in New Uzbekistan, its necessity, current issue, and its socio-philosophical classification and specific features were analyzed in this process.

Key words: pedagogue, status of pedagogue, integration, globalization, social, philosophical, transformation.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, in order to ensure the widespread involvement of the talented young generation and highly qualified personnel in pedagogical activities, it is necessary to present them with special rights and privileges, to implement a number of measures aimed at increasing the position of the pedagogue in society, including defining their status by a separate law. Based on this, a number of legal bases were developed in order to increase the status of the pedagogue in society, to regulate legal, social and economic relations related to the activity, to create conditions for professional development and to ensure legal guarantees.

The importance of studying the social position of the teacher is that his role in society is extremely high in almost any historical situation. The special importance of the teacher's social position is determined by his functions in the process of social reproduction and socialization of new generations.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Researchers such as V.P. Bezdukhov, E.P. Belozertsev, E.V. Bondarevskaya, N.M. Boritko, V.I. Zagvyazinsky, E.F. Zer, L.B. Itelson, Yu.N.A. Kulyutkin, V.S.S. Sukhobskaya have conducted scientific research on the description of the teacher's status and its formation. Philosophy in solving this problem (V.K. Lukashevich, T.A. Zagruzina); sociology (E.S. Zorina, A.I. Kravchenko), psychology (K.A. Abulkhanova-Slavskaya, B.G. Ananyev, A.G. Asmolov, B.F. Lomov, A.K. Markova, B D. Parigin, A.V. Petrovsky, V.I. Slobodchikov, A.S.S.); studies were conducted in the field of sociology of education (I.E. Zadorojniuk, E. Durkheim), social psychology (G.M. Andreeva, J. Myers).

In addition, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Status of the Pedagogue" serves as the main source.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Today, many legal documents have been adopted by the leadership of our country in order to educate a competent generation in the country, which, first of all, in these documents, educate the youth of the future as a generation that is competent in all aspects, physically healthy, mentally mature and will make a great contribution to the development of the country. is set as a goal.

The development of any field, the enrichment of human intelligence, is definitely based on science and education. The development of the education system ensures the

success of society in all spheres. After all, where there is no knowledge, there will be no change, development and renewal.

In the process of transformation of social institutions, a new status of a pedagogue is formed, its functions increase due to the introduction of information and communication technologies into the educational process. The 21st century is the age of specialists with high intellectual potential, modern knowledge and skills, a new outlook and independent thinking. The service of teachers in raising such a generation is incomparable. Because now in the world, the level of development of the country is determined by the position of pedagogues in the society.

Science and education is a problem that will solve the society and the state today, but also tomorrow. Therefore, in our country, great attention is being paid to this issue at the state level. Where youth education is left to its own devices, society will decline. The profoundly meaningful words of our enlightened grandfather Abdulla Avloni, "Education is for us a matter of life - or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or disaster" have not lost their value over time.

We are a nation of children who live for the future and happiness of their children. In this sense, we entrust the fate and future of our children to the hands of the teacher who considers him "as great as your father". Their hard work and the light they shed on the way to the bright future of young people cannot be compared or evaluated with anything. What we have achieved today is based on the contribution of our dear teachers and mentors.

Consideration of the place and role of the teacher in the social structure of modern society is related to the determination of the institutional functions of the educational system as a social institution. Social institutions and their tasks are analyzed in the works of M. Weber, T. Veblen, E. Durkheim, R. Darendorf, T. Parsons, G. Spencer, J. Smelser, J. Shepanski and others.

Education in a regional society is considered in the context of the development of social structure in connection with the changes occurring in the socio-economic life of the society as a social group. Methodological aspects of this problem were developed in the works of A. A. Galkina, Z. T. Golenkova, T. I. Zaslavskaya, V. I. Ilyin, V. V. Radaev, N. M. Rimashevskaya, R. V. Rybkina, F. E. Sheregi, and others. The sociology of adaptation processes occupies an important place in the research methodology. Adaptation problems are raised by biologists and scientifically based. Sociology approached the study of this process only at the beginning of the 20th century. The foundations of the theory of social adaptation were laid in the works of J. I. Bristol, F. Znanetsky, G. Chatterton-Hill, J. Thompson, M. Thorne and others. Currently, in the sociology of adaptation, status adaptation is not separated from adaptation types. Existing ideas about the processes of adaptation of teachers to their status as a socio-professional group differ from each other, only certain aspects of the problem (value, economic) are considered. The results of studying the way of life of teachers, their interaction with various social subjects are presented in the works of I. V. Bestujev-Lada, L. M. Drobijeva, E. G. Zborovsky, F. G. Ziyatdinova, L. P. Kapaeva and other scientists.

The Law "On the Status of Teachers" recently signed by the President was another practical expression of the high attention paid to teachers in our country. In this document, the rights, obligations, basic guarantees of the activities of pedagogues, payment of wages commensurate with their work, incentives and social protection principles were defined.

A pedagogue is a natural person who performs professional activities in the field of education and training and has the appropriate education, professional training and moral and ethical qualities in an educational organization on the basis of an employment contract concluded in accordance with legal documents.

The status of a pedagogue is recognized in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Organizational and legal conditions are created for pedagogues to carry out their professional activities, their social protection is ensured and guarantees are given for the realization of their rights.

The rights, honor, dignity and professional reputation of the teacher are under the protection of the state [1].

The pedagogue is invited to activities unrelated to his professional activity, but of political and social importance (participation in the process of organizing and holding elections, acting as an audience monitor during tests, assisting in population registration, to participate as an expert in the process of inspection and certification of educational organizations, etc.) according to his consent, based on the contract concluded with him, for an additional fee, during his free time or at his place of work The average salary is kept.

Administratively forcing a pedagogue to work in any form, as well as unlawfully interfering with a pedagogue's professional activity or preventing him from fulfilling his service obligations, is a cause of liability in accordance with the law [1].

Of course, if the reputation of teachers and coaches is restored, if their work is paid and encouraged, there will be changes in the quality of education. That's why respect for teachers is very high if you look at the examples of developed countries in the world. Because, first of all, high development and well-being can be achieved thanks to great attention to science and education. The most important goal and task facing our country is to join the ranks of developed democracies in the world, to build a free and prosperous way of life for our people. To accomplish such an honorable task, to build the third renaissance in our country, we rely on the work of pedagogues who have strong knowledge and potential, who are engineers of the human spirit, creators of the future.

In this regard, the system of values and ideological orientations of the pedagogical corps is changing. The nature of communication between people and the criteria for evaluating the quality of education and training are gradually changing. Thus, the relevance of studying the social status of teachers is determined by the dependence of the direction and speed of development of modern society on the socio-professional activity of teachers. Accordingly, sociological data are needed to objectively assess the situation and conditions of changing the status of teachers in society. The research is relevant in terms of using sociological data to understand the position of teachers in society, the possibilities and means of its positive change, which helps to increase the effectiveness of their professional activity.

CONCLUSION

Educators are subjects of growing personality formation and reflect the specific characteristics of ideas about educational goals in each historical period. Despite all the diversity of views on education, experience shows that the foundations of culture are laid in the early years. That is why all nations highly value the place of the teacher in the life of the society. People change society, and education changes people. At the center of education is the teacher. If we want to raise the educational work to a higher level, we must first of all raise the social status of teachers, teachers, mentors. Because, first of all, high development and well-being can be achieved thanks to great attention to science and education. The most important

goal and task facing our country is to join the ranks of developed democracies in the world, to build a free and prosperous way of life for our people.

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